

Multimodal IoT Device Authentication using Behavioral and Physical Unclonable Functions and Kyber Public Key Encryption

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Abstract— Proper device identity management and authentication is a must for many Internet of Things (IoT) applications. Physical Unclonable Functions (PUFs) are a well-known solution for identifying IoT devices. However, they can be attacked using both intrusive and non-intrusive physical attacks. In this work, we propose a multimodal device authentication scheme using Behavioral and Physical Unclonable Functions (BPUFs), which is a more secure option than PUFs. Adequate server-side security is achieved because BPUF responses are processed in the encrypted domain using homomorphic encryption. Furthermore, helper data attacks are avoided and the solution is quantum-safe. The proposal has been evaluated on an ESP32 microcontroller considering the security against false acceptance attacks and the security level of the Kyber public key encryption used. Fixing the first security to more than 192 bits for the behavioral and physical functions, the execution times of the cryptographic operations range from 41.30 to 205.70 ms, working at 160 MHz, with communication bandwidths from 3,840 to 15,680 bytes, and non-volatile memory occupation from 800 to 1,568 bytes.

Keywords—Device authentication, Hardware security, Physical unclonable functions, Behavioral unclonable functions, Post-quantum cryptography, Kyber

I. INTRODUCTION

Since Internet of Things (IoT) devices have access to sensitive information and can impact their immediate environment, it is critical to properly authenticate them, i.e., verify their identity and know if a rogue device, such as a counterfeit device, is in the field. Physical Unclonable Functions (PUFs) are a well-known solution for device authentication. In PUF circuits, random variations in the manufacturing process of a circuit are mapped into a bit string that can be used as identifier. The number of challenge-response pairs (CRPs) determines whether a PUF is weak or strong. Weak PUFs can support a relatively small number of CRPs, while strong PUFs can support a much larger number. However, invasive as well as non-invasive attacks are being discovered against physical responses of PUFs [1]-[3]. Thus, an attacker can supplant the identity of the device using a forged response. To remediate this, Behavioral and Physical Unclonable Functions (BPUFs) were introduced in [4]. They use an additional response called behavioral response that is computed using a set of physical responses. They are harder to attack since they use a dynamic behavior of a circuit instead of just the physical response. Hence, BPUFs can be viewed as a good construction for multimodal authentication.

Due to the advent of quantum computers, the data interchanged with the device during the authentication process should be protected with quantum-resistant primitives. Regarding public key encryption, Kyber Public Key Encryption (Kyber PKE), whose security is based on the

Module Learning With Errors (M-LWE) problem, is very suitable for IoT devices by its performance.

The work in [5] proposes a protocol using weak BPUFs with Kyber Key Encapsulation Mechanism (KEM). The behavioral response, besides being obfuscated, is encrypted by the device using the ephemeral key agreed with the remote server after the KEM. The obfuscated behavioral response is obtained by XORing the behavioral response with a pseudo-random string derived from a key reconstructed with a fresh physical response and the helper data stored at enrollment. A problem of this protocol is its vulnerability to helper-data attacks and low server-side security [6]. An interesting homomorphic property of Kyber PKE was introduced in [7]. This property is used in [8] to create a private and unimodal authentication scheme for IoT devices with weak PUFs that does not require helper data and processes sensitive data in an encrypted domain. This paper extends the protocol presented in [8], making it multimodal by using a BPUF. Thus, the solution has higher security, since a behavioral response must be attacked in addition to a physical response. Experimental results are given to illustrate the security against a false acceptance attack and the performance in terms of execution time, bandwidth, and non-volatile memory requirements of the IoT device.

The paper is structured as follows. Preliminaries are presented in Section II. Section III presents the proposed solution in this work. Experimental results are shown in Section IV. Finally, Section V concludes the paper.

II. PRELIMINARIES

Behavioral and Physical Unclonable Functions (BPUFs) were first introduced in [4]. Given a BPUF circuit, two functions are distinguished: the Physical Unclonable Function (PUF) and the Behavioral Unclonable Function (BUF).

For the measurement m , the b -th bit $u_m[b]$ of the *physical response* u is defined as

$$u_m[b] = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if PUF unit } b \text{ satisfies a condition} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

and, given $R + 1$ physical responses, the b -th bit $v_m[b]$ of the *behavioral response* v is computed as

$$v_m[b] = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \sum_{j=1}^R (u_0[b] \oplus u_j[b]) > 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where \oplus is the XOR operation.

In the case of an SRAM BPUF, the physical response is formed by the start-up values of a portion of the SRAM, and the behavioral response is formed by measuring the stability of those values after R start-ups.

Physical and behavioral responses can be used as device identifiers with the tuple $ID = (u, v)$. In an enrollment phase, a reference physical and behavioral responses u_0 and v_0 are stored, and, in an authentication phase i , new responses u_i and v_i are generated and compared with the stored ones.

Two physical responses can be compared using the Hamming distance as

$$HD(u_0, u_i) = HW(u_0 \oplus u_i) \quad (3)$$

where HW is the Hamming weight function. On the other hand, it has been shown in [4] that behavioral responses have a better distinguishability using the Jaccard distance. Since the Hamming weight cannot be computed in the encrypted domain with our proposal, we use an approximated Jaccard distance as

$$JD_{app}(v_0, v_i) = 2HD(v_0, v_i)/(HD(v_0, v_i) + 2G) \quad (5)$$

where G is a constant obtained in a characterization process as the expected Hamming weight of a behavioral response.

In the authentication phase, the device identifier is verified if $HD(u_0, u_i) \leq HD_{MAX}$ and $JD_{app}(v_0, v_i) \leq JD_{MAX}$. The value HD_{MAX} is obtained as explained in [8]. To obtain the value of JD_{MAX} , we first rewrite the expression (5) as

$$JD_{app}(v_0, v_i) = 2/(1 + 2(G/e)) \quad (6)$$

where e is the number of errors between v_i and v_0 . If E is the random variable associated with e , we assume that the probability that a genuine behavioral response contains more than e_{MAX} errors is given by

$$P_G(E > e_{MAX}) = 1 - \sum_{i=0}^{e_{MAX}} \binom{N}{i} p_{eG}^i (1 - p_{eG})^{N-i} \quad (7)$$

where N is the number of bits in the responses and p_{eG} is the bit error probability in the genuine responses, which can be obtained experimentally using the average fractional Hamming distance between the genuine behavioral responses. In this way, e_{MAX} can be chosen to achieve $P_G(E > e_{MAX}) < \epsilon$, where ϵ is the allowed false rejection rate of the behavioral response, and can be used in (6) to calculate the JD_{MAX} value.

Given that the attacker can know the Hamming weight of the reference behavioral response M , the size N , and the value of JD_{MAX} , the probability of success of a false acceptance attack is given by a cumulative hypergeometric distribution that is maximum when the Hamming weight of the responses that s/he tries is $n_{optimal}$. The details about this attack probability can be seen in [4].

Concerning the preliminaries about the cryptographic operations employed in our proposal, Kyber PKE is defined by key generation, encryption and decryption algorithms. The three algorithms can be found in [9]. The key generation algorithm ($KYBER.PKE.keygen()$) generates a secret key $sk = s$ and a public key $pk = (t, \rho)$. The encryption algorithm ($KYBER.PKE.encrypt(m, pk)$) uses the public key pk to encrypt a plaintext message m , and generates a ciphertext $c = (u, v)$. The message is represented as a polynomial with coefficients in $\{0,1\}$. The encryption scheme ($KYBER.PKE.decrypt(c, sk)$) takes a ciphertext c and the secret key sk and returns the message m . The work in [7] found that the Kyber PKE satisfies the following homomorphic property given two ciphertexts c_1 and c_2 of two messages m_1 and m_2 :

$$KYBER.PKE.decrypt(POLY.subtract(c_1, c_2)) = m_1 \oplus m_2 \quad (8)$$

where the function $POLY.subtract(c_1, c_2)$ performs the coefficient-wise subtractions between the ciphertexts, that is, $u_1 - u_2$ and $v_1 - v_2$. It is assumed that the ciphertexts are decompressed and the result is recompressed. Thus, with this homomorphic property, an XOR operation between two plaintexts can be performed between two strings in the encrypted domain.

III. PROPOSED SOLUTION FOR MULTIMODAL DEVICE AUTHENTICATION

A. Assumptions

We distinguish three parties in the scheme. One party is the IoT device (DEV) whose authenticity needs to be verified in the field. The other parties are two servers responsible for managing the identity of DEV: the Database Server (DBS), which stores the information needed to authenticate DEV in a private and secure manner, and the Authentication Server (AS), which proves the authenticity of DEV. DBS and AS are considered to behave honestly. We assume that the communication channels are secure between DBS and DEV, AS and DEV, and between DBS and AS. For simplicity, and because we are focusing on device authentication, we will not show this.

Also, we assume that DEV has a BPUF, which generates proper physical and behavioral responses. $BPUF.getPUFresp()$ and $BPUF.getBUFresp()$ are the functions for generating these responses. In general, both responses come from different challenges. Also, DEV should have a True Random Number Generator (TRNG).

We assume that AS knows the threshold distance HD_{MAX} of the physical response and the threshold distance JD_{MAX} of the behavioral response, which is securely provided by the device manufacturer. Also, AS has already executed the Kyber key generation algorithm and has the secret key SK and the public key PK .

B. Enrollment phase

In the enrollment phase, the identity of DEV is registered by DBS. The enrollment phase is performed only once, and it should be done in a controlled and secure manner.

First, DBS gives to DEV the challenges of the physical and behavioral responses (c_{PUF} , c_{BUF}), the public key PK , and its identifier ID_{DEV} , which is chosen by AS. Given the received challenges, DEV generates the physical response u_0 and the behavioral response v_0 . Then, DEV uses the Kyber encryption algorithm and PK to encrypt the physical and behavioral responses, resulting in the protected physical response U_0 and the protected behavioral response V_0 . Finally, DEV sends U_0 and V_0 to DBS to be stored. DEV stores ID_{DEV} along with PK .

C. Authentication phase

In the authentication phase, DEV is in the field and ready to operate. In this phase, AS wants to verify the identity of DEV for an authentication i . This is done through the steps shown in Figure 1.

Firstly, AS generates a pair of nonces n_i^u and n_i^v to guarantee the freshness of the process and to prevent a possible impersonation of DBS and DEV. Then, AS sends to DBS a request to start the authentication phase and the identifier of DEV, ID_{DEV} . The AS also sends to DEV a request to perform an authentication, ID_{DEV} and the nonces n_i^u and

Fig. 1. Steps performed at the authentication phase.

n_i^v . DBS sends to DEV the challenges to the BPUF of the device, c_{PUF} and c_{BUF} .

DEV samples a fresh physical response u_i and a fresh behavioral response v_i , which are XORed with the nonces n_i^u and n_i^v , respectively. The values $u_i \oplus n_i^u$ and $v_i \oplus n_i^v$ are encrypted using Kyber encryption algorithm, and the public key PK , resulting in U_i and V_i . These values are sent to DBS.

Then, DBS performs the $POLY.substruct$ operation between the reference and fresh physical response U_0 and U_i , and between the reference and fresh behavioral responses V_0 and V_i . The results are the encrypted differences D_i^u and D_i^v , which are sent to AS. Finally, AS decrypts the differences, performs the XOR with the nonces, resulting in d_i^u and d_i^v , and obtains the Hamming distance between u_0 and u_i , and the approximated Jaccard distance between v_0 and v_i . These distances are compared with the thresholds HD_{MAX} and JD_{MAX} to check if the device is successfully authenticated.

D. Features of the proposal

The device uses two responses to authenticate itself instead of just one, resulting in a stronger authentication. Also, the responses are never seen in plaintext due to the use of homomorphic encryption. So, if the authentication server is attacked, the attacker cannot see the responses directly. In addition, helper-data attacks are completely avoided since no helper data are used in the protocol. Even more, we argue that behavioral responses are more difficult to clone than physical responses using an invasive attack. This is because behavioral responses are sensitive to the reliability of a set of physical responses. If an invasive attack is performed, it would affect the reliability of the circuit, which would change the behavioral response. Also, the proposal is ready for the quantum-era because we use Kyber public key encryption. In addition, a device can use a single CRP to authenticate to many database and authentication servers because the response is never seen in clear and they are unlinkable. [7].

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Regarding the experimental results, in this work we focus on the IoT device. A Pycom WiPy 3.0 board with an Espressif ESP32 microcontroller was chosen to evaluate the proposal. The board has 8 MB of external flash memory. The ESP32

microcontroller has 512 kB of internal SRAM. A clock frequency of 160 MHz was chosen for the experiments. The internal TRNG of the ESP32 was used to generate the required random numbers of the proposal. We use the ESP32 internal SRAM as the SRAM BPUF and characterized it by using 25,593 bytes and 7 boards and taking 2000 measurements from each board with a 5-second delay between measurements using the deep sleep mode. The evaluation of the behavioral responses was carried out using three values of R , 10, 20 and 40, and three different response sizes, 768, 1,024 and 2,048 bits. We evaluated our proposal using the reference implementation of Kyber found in [10].

A. Parameter selection and security evaluation

Table I shows the values of the average intra approximated Jaccard distance and the average inter approximated Jaccard distance as a function of the parameter R and the size of the behavioral responses. Note that these are the Jaccard approximated distances reformulated in Section II. It can be seen that the size does not significantly affect these values. However, the difference between the average intra and inter distances increases slightly as R increases. G represents the average Hamming weight in the behavioral responses.

The maximum number of allowed errors in an authentication e_{MAX} and the threshold JD_{MAX} have been evaluated as explained in Section II. They are shown in Table I. It can be seen that e_{MAX} is slightly lower as R increases. The maximum probability of a successful false acceptance attack, ($Prob.attack$) referred in Section II has been evaluated, adapted to the approximated Jaccard distance used in this paper. The values are also shown in Table I together with the corresponding optimal values that the attacker should select for the Hamming weight of the trial ($n_{optimal}$) and the lowest number of successes or 1's that the attacker hit (s_{attack}) employed to calculate $Prob.attack$. Bit security, calculated as $\log_2(1/Prob.attack)$ is also shown in Table I. These values can be used to select appropriate values of R and behavioral response sizes. In this case, if a bit security higher than 192 is desired, the values of 2,048 bits, 1,024 bits and 768 bits are depicted for R values of 10, 20 and 40, respectively.

For physical responses, the choice of HD_{MAX} and the bit security can be seen evaluated in [8]. A size of 512 bits can be

TABLE I. PARAMETER SELECTION AND SECURITY EVALUATION (HIGHLIGHTED IN GREY, FOR A BIT SECURITY HIGHER THAN 192)

R	Size (bits)	$JD_{app,intra}$	$JD_{app,inter}$	G	e_{MAX}	JD_{MAX}	$n_{optimal}$	s_{attack}	Prob. attack	Bit security
10	768	0.3602	0.9206	111.3586	86	0.5571	30	27	$3.0160 \cdot 10^{-21}$	68
	1,024	0.3605	0.9208	148.4655	108	0.5334	48	43	$2.0526 \cdot 10^{-33}$	108
	2,048	0.3609	0.9212	296.9194	191	0.4867	128	116	$4.9130 \cdot 10^{-92}$	303
20	768	0.2792	0.9026	135.1027	79	0.4525	69	62	$4.9149 \cdot 10^{-45}$	147
	1,024	0.2795	0.9028	180.125	99	0.4311	98	89	$5.8316 \cdot 10^{-66}$	216
	2,048	0.2797	0.9030	360.2377	174	0.3891	223	204	$1.6605 \cdot 10^{-155}$	514
40	768	0.2256	0.8859	156.3017	74	0.3828	99	90	$4.5027 \cdot 10^{-63}$	207
	1,024	0.2257	0.8860	208.3925	92	0.3616	139	127	$1.5300 \cdot 10^{-90}$	298
	2,048	0.2259	0.8862	416.7716	161	0.3238	303	279	$4.3141 \cdot 10^{-205}$	678

chosen to achieve a bit security above 192 bits, which should use a value of 56 for HD_{MAX} .

B. Performance of the proposal

The performance of the proposal was evaluated as a function of the behavioral response parameter R and the Kyber instance. The response sizes were chosen according to the desired bit security of 192 bits for both responses. Of course, this security can be decreased for many applications. Table II shows the results of the communication bandwidth and the execution time of the cryptographic operations of the device. The results are considering both physical and behavioral responses. Bandwidth values range from 3,840 to 15,680 bytes, and cryptographic execution times range from 41.30 to 205.70 ms, depending on the selected R and Kyber instance. Higher values are for an R value of 10. However, a lower R value requires fewer responses to form a behavioral response, thus saving time during the ESP32's deep sleep.

TABLE II. PERFORMANCE OF THE PROPOSAL

R	Kyber instance	Bandwidth (bytes)	Exec. times (ms)
10	KYBER512	7,680	82.60
	KYBER768	10,880	135.40
	KYBER1024	15,680	205.70
20	KYBER512	4,608	49.56
	KYBER768	6,528	81.24
	KYBER1024	9,408	123.42
40	KYBER512	3,840	41.30
	KYBER768	5,440	67.70
	KYBER1024	7,840	102.85

Note that no calculations are performed during deep sleep, so it is not expected to consume much power. Regarding the non-volatile memory required for the device, it is related to the size of the public key (which is 800, 1,184 or 1,568 bytes), depending on the used Kyber instance. The size of the identifier depends on the application, but it can be of 32 bytes.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we propose a multimodal device authentication scheme based on physical and behavioral unclonable functions. The proposal has a very high security not only because the security provided by each response is added but also because the responses are processed in the encrypted domain thanks to the homomorphic encryption. Also, helper-data attacks are avoided. The solution is ready for the quantum era by using Kyber public key encryption scheme. Experimental results on an ESP32 microcontroller

show that high security against false acceptance attacks is achieved with low execution times for the cryptographic operations. Concerning non-volatile storage, the requirements are low.

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